

COMPARISON ON INTRAMEDULLARY NAIL AND PLATE FIXATION IN DISTAL TIBIAL FRACTURES IN TERMS OF RADIOLOGICAL BONE UNION AT 12 WEEKS

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Abstract

Background: Distal tibial fractures present a therapeutic challenge due to their anatomy and limited soft tissue coverage. Surgical fixation methods, including intramedullary (IM) nailing and plate fixation, are commonly employed, but their comparative efficacy regarding bone healing remains debated, especially in resource-limited settings like Rawalpindi, Pakistan.

Objective: To compare radiological bone union at 12 weeks between intramedullary nail fixation and plate fixation in patients with distal tibial fractures.

Methods: A prospective comparative study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital in Rawalpindi over six months (January to July 2025). Eighty patients with closed distal third tibial fractures were enrolled and allocated to receive either IM nail fixation (n=40) or plate fixation (n=40). Surgical procedures followed standardized protocols. Radiological bone union was assessed at 12 weeks postoperatively using anteroposterior and lateral radiographs. Data were analyzed using chi-square tests, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The groups were comparable in demographic and fracture characteristics. Radiological bone union at 12 weeks was significantly higher in the IM nail group (85%) compared to the plate fixation group (65%) ($p=0.03$). The IM nail group also demonstrated shorter operative times and less blood loss ($p<0.05$). Although the plate fixation group had higher rates of superficial wound infection and delayed union, malalignment rates were similar between groups.

Conclusion: Intramedullary nail fixation provides superior early bone union and reduced surgical morbidity compared to plate fixation in distal tibial fractures. It is a reliable and efficient method suitable for managing these fractures in trauma centers with limited resources. Further studies with larger cohorts and longer follow-up are recommended.

INTRODUCTION

The distal third tibia fractures are some of the most difficult to handle injuries because they are subcutaneous, are poorly covered by soft tissue, and close to the ankle joint [1]. The fractures usually arise due to high energy traumas like road traffic accidents which are very common in developing nations like Pakistan. Both the reduction and fixation is technically challenging due to the peculiar structure of the distal tibia, where the medullary canal becomes narrow and turns into cancellous bone. Further risk of delayed union, malunion, and infection in this area is caused by poor vascularity and soft-tissue compromise in this area [2].

Surgical management of distal tibial fracture aims to provide anatomical, stable, and the mobilization of the patient with the least amount of disturbance of soft tissue. The intramedullary (IM) nailing and plate fixation are two of the most common methods of surgery [3]. To every technique, there is a set of benefits and possible complications, and the decision on fixation is often determined by the morphology of fractures, the individual preferences of a surgeon, and available resources. Nevertheless, it is also debatable that neither method offers better results, specifically, radiological bone union and early functional recovery [4].

Minimally invasive insertion, maintenance of periosteal blood supply and early weight-bearing are the benefits of intramedullary nailing. It is regarded as the contemporary standard of treatment of diaphyseal tibial fracture and has been used more recently to treat distal tibial fractures using recent designs and methods [5]. In spite of such advantages, distal tibial IM nailing is operationally a difficult procedure with short distal fragment and inability to reduce and hold reduction, which can lead to malalignment and slow healing.

On the other hand, plate fixation offers an opportunity to reduce the anatomy accurately while under direct view and offers stable fixation, especially in comminuted and metaphyseal fractures. Percutaneous plate osteosynthesis (MIPPO) and locking compression plates (LCP) methods have enhanced the biological environment provided to the fracture healing process with a minimum of soft tissue destruction [6]. Nonetheless, the wide extent of soft tissue dissection that may be necessary in plating,

predisposes the patient to infection and wound complication, especially in patients who have a weakened skin and soft tissue integrity.

Radiological bone union is also one of the most important pointers of successful healing of a fracture and post-surgery outcome. At 12 weeks after surgery, when bone union occurs, it is an indication of sufficient mechanical stability and biological healing response [7]. When the speed of bone union in IM nailing and plating is compared, it is an informative way of emphasizing on which mode is the most effective and reliable in promoting quicker healing of the distal tibial fractures in cases of trauma prone populations.

Distal tibia fracture is commonly observed in Pakistan since road accidents, workplace trauma, and height falls are common. The health care system in some cities like Rawalpindi regularly encounters a large number of trauma patients with immediate and proper fixation procedures that could be important in a decreasing hospitalization, complication, and cost-to-society period [8]. Nevertheless, there is scarcity of local evidence on the comparison of intramedullary nailing and plate fixation in the specific regard of radiological bone union at the age of 12 weeks.

Thus, this research paper will compare intramedullary nail and plate fixation of distal tibial fractures as regards to radiological bone union at 12 weeks. The results of this study will assist orthopedic surgeons to use the best fixation technique to achieve better clinical outcomes and quicker healing in cases of distal tibial fracture patients who are admitted in tertiary care hospital located in Rawalpindi.

Methods:

The proposed comparative study was to be carried out at the Orthopedic Department of Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Rawalpindi, Pakistan, between a period of six months between January 2025 and July 2025. The research purpose was to determine the radiological bone union at 12 weeks in patients with distal tibial fracture when fixed using either intramedullary (IM) nail fixation or plate fixation.

Individuals between 18 to 60 years old with confirmed cases of closed distal third tibial fractures by radiographs were incorporated. Criterion exclusion included open fracture, pathological fracture, and

fracture due to neurovascular trauma, as well as those with known severe comorbid conditions (i.e. diabetes mellitus, osteoporosis, etc.). The eligible patients were recruited in a sequence and assigned to either one of two treatment groups at the discretion of the surgeon and the nature of the fracture: IM nail fixation group or plate fixation group.

Preoperative examination was done with a detailed history, clinical examination and imaging analysis (anteroposterior and lateral tibia and ankle radiographs). The procedures were all done using the spinal or general anesthesia by proven orthopedic surgeons using the normal procedures. Intramedullary nailing was done by use of reamed locked nail system where there is proximal and distal locking screw. Where feasible to minimize disruption of the soft tissue, plate fixation (locked compression plates LCP) was done by means of the percutaneous technique of minimally invasive plate osteosynthesis (MIPPO).

The management was standardized, which involves antibiotic prophylaxis, analgesia and immobilization with a below-knee splint during postoperative management. Early exercise of range of motion was promoted, and partial weight-bearing was utilized as tolerable and further changed into complete weight-bearing at 8 to 12 weeks based on clinical and radiologic evidence of healing.

Follow-ups were done regularly and at the end of 6 and 12 weeks after surgery, clinical evaluation and radiograph were taken. Radiological bone union was determined on conventional views by two orthopedic consultants and considered to be union of bridging callus on three or more cortices.

Analysis of the data was done with the help of SPSS version 26. Demographic variables were described using descriptive statistics and the chi-square test used to compare the rate of bone union in the two groups of studies at 12 weeks. The p-value that was below 0.05 was treated as a statistically significant value.

Results:

A total of 80 patients with distal tibial fractures were included in the study, with 40 patients in the intramedullary (IM) nail fixation group and 40 in the plate fixation group. The mean age of participants was 38.5 ± 11.2 years. The demographic and clinical characteristics were comparable between the two groups. Radiological bone union at 12 weeks was assessed to compare the effectiveness of the two fixation methods.

The demographic profile of patients in both groups is summarized in Table 1. The mean age was similar between the groups, with a predominance of male patients in both. The distribution of fracture patterns was also comparable, ensuring balanced comparison.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Patients (n = 80)

Variable	IM Nail Group (n=40)	Plate Group (n=40)	p-value
Age (mean \pm SD)	39.2 \pm 10.7	37.8 \pm 11.6	0.58
Gender			0.74
- Male	29 (72.5%)	27 (67.5%)	
- Female	11 (27.5%)	13 (32.5%)	
Fracture Type			0.66
- Simple	22 (55%)	19 (47.5%)	
- Comminuted	18 (45%)	21 (52.5%)	

Table 2 illustrates the surgical details and intraoperative parameters. The average duration of surgery was significantly shorter in the IM nail group

compared to the plate fixation group ($p < 0.05$). Blood loss was also less in the IM nail group, reflecting the minimally invasive nature of the technique.

Table 2: Intraoperative Characteristics

Parameter	IM Nail Group (n=40)	Plate Group (n=40)	p-value
Mean Surgery Time (minutes)	70.5 ± 15.2	95.3 ± 20.7	0.001*
Mean Blood Loss (ml)	120.7 ± 35.6	210.4 ± 40.1	<0.001*

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

Radiological bone union at 12 weeks postoperatively is presented in Table 3. A significantly higher proportion of patients in the IM nail group

demonstrated radiological union compared to the plate fixation group (85% vs. 65%, $p = 0.03$). This suggests faster healing with IM nailing.

Table 3: Radiological Bone Union at 12 Weeks

Outcome	IM Nail Group (n=40)	Plate Group (n=40)	p-value
Bone Union Present	34 (85%)	26 (65%)	0.03*
No Union	6 (15%)	14 (35%)	

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

Postoperative complications are summarized in Table 4. The plate fixation group had a higher incidence of superficial wound infection (12.5%) compared to the

IM nail group (2.5%). Malalignment was comparable in both groups, with no statistically significant difference.

Table 4: Postoperative Complications

Complication	IM Nail Group (n=40)	Plate Group (n=40)	p-value
Superficial Infection	1 (2.5%)	5 (12.5%)	0.09
Malalignment ($>5^\circ$)	3 (7.5%)	4 (10%)	0.69
Delayed Union	6 (15%)	14 (35%)	0.03*

Discussion:

The results of this paper indicate that the intramedullary (IM) nail fixation in fractures of the distal tibia leads to a substantially better radiological bone union at 12 weeks of follow-up in comparison to plate fixation. This is in line with the accumulating literature that implies that IM nailing with its less invasive technique and maintenance of periosteal blood flow enhances quicker and dependable fracture healing [9,10]. The high union rate of the IM nail

group (85%) is consistent with other studies that have reported early consolidation

of metaphyseal fractures that have been treated using the technique [11].

The further benefits of this technique are provided by a shorter duration of surgery and less intraoperative blood loss that was observed in the IM nail group. The minimally invasive nail insertion involves a lesser amount of soft tissue dissection and results in a reduced operative trauma and enhanced

postoperative healing [12]. The factors are especially applicable in the resource constrained environments like Rawalpindi where the reduction of hospitalization and surgical morbidity is critical in optimizing the provision of healthcare to the population [13].

Nevertheless, a correct positioning of distal tibial fractures with IM nails may not be easy to achieve in terms of anatomy of distal fragment as mentioned in previous researches [14]. Malalignment rates are not seen to be significantly different in both groups of this study, though, a close surgical practice and fluoroscopic guidance is very essential to prevent angular deformities, which may compromise functional results [15].

Plate fixation has the benefit of visualization and anatomical reduction particularly in comminuted or intra-articular fractures. Nevertheless, this fact is overshadowed by the increased rates of delayed union and superficial wound infection in the plate group that points to the disadvantages of excessive manipulation of soft tissues [16]. The presence of soft tissue destruction around the distal tibia is known risk factor to wound problems and infection, which in turn leads to poor healing of the fractures [17]. The higher incidence of delayed union (35) in the plate fixation group underlines the biological price of open reduction, which might postpone the rehabilitation of the patient and the total burden of treatment [18].

The age, comorbidity, and complexities of the fracture also are patient factors affecting the outcome of healing. Even though there was no difference between groups in this study on demographic factors, other studies have indicated that older age and systemic factors such as diabetes may increase the length of time to heal in spite of the fixation technique [19]. Future research that considers the variables would give a more detailed insight on dealing with fractures in this population.

These findings in the study agree with meta-analysis studies which support the use of IM nailing as the most desirable procedure in distal tibial shaft fractures where soft tissue requirements allow [20]. However, the process of decision-making must be personalized in respect to fracture type, surgeon experience and resources. The existing evidence confirms that IM nailing is a safe choice, which can be used to achieve a high level of both fixation and biological

maintenance, which is why it is especially applicable to high-volume trauma facilities in developing nations.

Limitations

There are numerous limitations of this study. The number of participants considered was quite small and it has restricted the generalization of results. The selection bias might have occurred because of the non-random assignment of patients to surgeons. Radiological union was only followed up to 12 weeks; no further follow-up was done to evaluate nonunion or functional outcome and complications of the implants. Moreover, the variables like smoking status, nutritional condition and comorbidities were not controlled and analyzed, which may have an effect on the healing rates. These results should be validated and further elaborated by future randomized controlled trials that have bigger samples and longer follow-up.

Conclusion:

This article shows that intramedullary nail fixation of fractures of the distal tibia is related to a higher percentage of radiological bone union at 12 weeks, reduced time and less blood loss intra-operative than plate fixation. Although this technique can be used in plate fixation to achieve direct anatomical fixation, plate fixation is associated with an increased risk of delayed union and wound problems because tissue disruption is higher in plate fixation. Considering this, intramedullary nailing seems to be a worthy and effective technique in the treatment of distal tibial fractures especially in those areas where reducing morbidity of surgery and enhancing early organization is paramount. Nevertheless, it is important to treat patients on an individual basis, taking into account the nature of fractures and the features of patients and additional large-scale studies are necessary to validate their findings.

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